

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

DESIGN OF A SYSTEM FOR ANALYSIS AND FORECASTING OF AIR QUALITY

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Abstract

The article addresses the issue of air pollution, which poses serious threats to public health and the environment, according to the World Health Organization. The current state of research and technologies in air quality monitoring and forecasting, as well as existing commercial and scientific projects, are described. It is determined that one of the key tasks is providing accessible information to the public about air pollution levels, enabling timely responses to environmental threats.

The article presents the development of an intelligent automated system for monitoring and forecasting air pollution levels. The system is based on modern data analysis methods and neural networks, allowing for pollution level predictions up to six hours in advance. The primary goal of this work is to create a solution that combines the high accuracy of scientific models with accessibility and ease of use for a broad audience. The system provides information in an easy-to-understand format through visualization on a web platform, using Air Quality Indexes (AQI), enabling non-experts to quickly assess health risks.

The article also discusses key modern approaches to air pollution forecasting, such as autoregressive models (ARIMAX), regression analysis, and artificial neural networks (ANN), which were employed in the development of the system. The technical aspects of the system are described in detail, including the architecture of the three-tier client-server model, data processing algorithms, and the functional capabilities of the web client for real-time user interaction with the system.

The project covers more than 30 cities in Ukraine and collects data from over 100 monitoring stations, allowing for highly accurate air quality forecasting. The web service updates pollution status data every hour, while weather conditions are updated every 15 minutes. By using scalable architecture, the system can handle a large volume of requests and ensure continuous access to up-to-date data.

The study's results demonstrated that the developed system can forecast air pollution levels with an accuracy of up to 72% for a six-hour prediction window, confirming the effectiveness of the approach used. The model was tested on real data for Kyiv, and the results showed a high correlation between the predicted and actual air quality values.

The proposed system is a promising tool for monitoring and forecasting air quality, contributing to the improvement of environmental conditions and the protection of public health.

Keywords: system, forecasting, monitoring, data analysis, neural networks.

Introduction. According to the World Health Organization's 2023 data, polluted air causes approximately seven million deaths annually, accounting for 1/8 of all deaths worldwide. Air pollution also increases the incidence of asthma, particularly among children, raising the risk of developing the disease by 17%. This makes air quality one of the key public health concerns.

One of the important tasks is forecasting atmospheric pollution levels, which can help warn the public about environmental threats and enhance air quality control. This will help protect people's health and ensure better environmental conditions. Air quality monitoring is also a promising area of research, as global attention to environmental issues continues to grow.

Monitoring technologies can be used by businesses to adjust outdoor work schedules and by government agencies to warn the public of dangerous pollution levels and organize safe events.

The aim of this work is to design an intelligent automated system that will monitor and forecast atmospheric air pollution levels. This will allow timely warn-

ings to the public and organizations about potential environmental threats, contributing to the protection of health and the improvement of environmental conditions.

Current State of the Problem. To date, a significant number of studies have been conducted in the field of air pollution monitoring and forecasting [1-4], and interest in this area continues to grow. Numerous models have been developed for predicting air pollution levels using various technologies. One of the most popular tools for forecasting future air quality is data mining. In particular, models based on decision trees [2], regression analysis [3], and neural networks [4] have been developed. However, the most commonly used models are based on autoregressive models (ARIMAX) [5, 6], which compete with neural network models (ANN) [7-9].

In addition to scientific developments, several commercial projects aimed at the general public have recently been created to forecast air quality. Examples of such products include AQICN [10], AirNow [11], and PlumeLabs [12].

In Ukraine, there are regional websites [13, 14] that publish data on atmospheric air pollution. However, this data is presented in quantitative metrics understandable only to environmental specialists, without visual representation, which makes the information difficult for the general public to comprehend. As a result, citizens are unable to properly assess the danger of outdoor exposure and the potential health risks.

Foreign counterparts are more accessible for non-experts to understand, but they either do not provide information on pollution levels in Ukraine or fail to account for the specificities of national air quality control and monitoring processes.

Research Results. Air quality is determined by the concentration of pollutants, which can change hourly due to factors such as emission levels, time of day, and weather conditions. Most air pollution is caused by four main substances: particulate matter, carbon dioxide, nitrogen oxides, and carbon monoxide, whose concentrations often exceed permissible limits. Air quality indexes (AQI) are used to inform the public, calculated based on pollutant concentrations over a specific period. These indexes help visually represent pollution levels and provide recommendations to reduce its harmful effects on health. However, different countries use different air quality indexes, with the American AQI being the most widespread.

One of the main challenges in air quality research is the need for continuous monitoring, which requires an extensive network of observation stations. Air quality forecasting is complicated by three factors:

- air quality depends on many variables, such as weather conditions, traffic, industrial emissions, etc., and not all data is publicly available;
- pollution levels can change rapidly throughout the day and vary across different parts of a city, especially in industrial areas;
- air quality can shift drastically due to extreme weather conditions or unforeseen circumstances, making accurate forecasting more difficult.

System Requirements for Air Quality Analysis and Forecasting. After analyzing existing systems,

their best qualities were identified: the predictive accuracy of research projects and the simplicity and convenience of commercial products. This combination allows the provision of real-time air pollution information in an accessible format while ensuring a high-quality forecast. The system must also feature an open API for integration with other projects.

The developed data collection, storage, and analysis system will function as a web service with an open API, and the client side will be a website. It is planned to cover more than 30 cities in Ukraine, collecting data from over 100 monitoring stations. Pollution data will be updated hourly, and weather data every 15 minutes, requiring the system to process approximately 10,000 requests per day and store over 10 MB of data daily. System scalability is designed to ensure efficient processing.

Key project requirements include data relevance, accessibility, and accuracy, as well as clear visualization for users. The system will collect data around the clock from various sources, process it to ensure accuracy, and present the information in a simple and understandable format, including map visualization and the Air Quality Index (AQI).

System Design. An analysis of the subject area revealed that air pollution levels can be predicted based on factors such as current air quality, weather conditions, weather forecasts, as well as the time of day and the day of the week. Research has confirmed the correlation between air quality and these characteristics [15]. The designed model will utilize this data to forecast pollution levels.

The forecast will be made for each AQI pollutant, hourly, for each monitoring station. The forecast horizon will be 6 hours, which is the standard for short-term predictions [1, 16, 17]. To implement this model, multilayer neural networks were chosen.

The system is designed with a three-tier client-server architecture, consisting of a web client, an application server, and a database server. The system components (Fig. 1) are as follows:

Figure 1. System components

1. Web Client – a website that visualizes data obtained through requests to the web service on the application server.

2. Application Server – contains all the business logic of the system.

3. Database – stores data on monitoring stations, pollutant information, current weather and its forecast, as well as air quality forecast data.

The application server retrieves information from government websites and private web services (data sources) that provide real-time meteorological data and air quality information. The application server includes a web service where the system's business logic is implemented, including forecasting, data processing, and analysis. The web service consists of four main components (Fig. 2):

Figure 2. System components diagram

1. Data Collector – an automated system that continuously collects open data from external sources in real-time via web services or web scraping for analysis and air pollution forecasting.

2. Data Augmentation Component – fills in missing values from monitoring stations by using data from their spatial or temporal neighbors.

3. Pollution Forecaster – contains a model that predicts the air quality index (AQI) values for each pollutant at each station for the next six hours.

4. REST Service – facilitates the transmission of information via the HTTP protocol, allowing clients to retrieve data on forecasts and current atmospheric conditions.

Based on the requirements for the web service, a use case diagram (Fig. 3) was developed, which includes five use cases and a single actor – the developer, who interacts with the service.

Figure 3. Use case diagram for the web service.

The developer is a specialist engaged in developing software systems. All use cases on the diagram are initiated through HTTP requests to the web service, and responses are provided in JSON format. By executing requests, the developer can:

- retrieve a list of monitoring stations or data about a specific station;
- obtain current information about air pollution and weather in a selected city or area;
- get an hourly forecast of weather and pollution for a specified city;
- access a multi-day forecast of weather and pollution for the selected city and its surrounding areas.

This functionality provides flexibility in accessing real-time environmental data and pollution forecasts, ensuring the system is useful for both immediate and long-term planning.

The air quality forecasting model is based on four sets of data for the current hour (t) and the next hour (t+1). These datasets include:

- air quality for t;
- meteorological data for t;
- weather forecast for t+1;
- hour of the day and day of the week.

The input vectors for the neural network are structured as follows:

$$\begin{cases} mn_{t+1} = (\text{weather state, temperature, wind speed,} \\ \quad \text{wind direction, humidity}) \\ DT_{t+1} = (\text{day of the week, hour of the day}) \\ mn_{t+2} = (\text{weather state, temperature, wind speed,} \\ \quad \text{wind direction, humidity}) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The output of the neural network is a single value: $AQI_{t+1} - AQI$, the Air Quality Index of a pollutant for t+1.

Neural Network Structure. Based on the input data, we determined the appropriate number of layers in the neural network. With 13 characteristics and a 3-month dataset, a three-layer neural network with one hidden layer is the most suitable. A two-layer network is insufficient for modeling the necessary function, while increasing the number of layers to four results in degraded performance.

All three layers are fully connected (Dense layers), and the activation function chosen is ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit). The structure of the neural network is illustrated in Figure 4:

- the input layer receives 13 values, including weather data and pollution levels for time t, as well as the weather forecast for t+1. It has 13 neurons;
- the hidden layer contains 30 neurons;
- the output layer consists of a single neuron, as the output is a single predicted value – the AQI of the pollutant for t+1.

Figure 4. The structure of the neural network

Accuracy Calculation. To evaluate the effectiveness of the model and compare it with other models, the forecast accuracy is calculated using the following formula:

$$p = 1 - \frac{|\hat{\alpha} - \alpha|}{n}, \quad (2)$$

where:

- $\hat{\alpha}$ is the predicted AQI value,
- α is the actual (true) AQI value,
- n is the number of predictions.

This method allows for determining how much the predicted value deviates from the actual value, thereby assessing the model's accuracy.

The conducted tests showed that the developed model is capable of predicting air pollution levels with an accuracy of ($p = 0.719$) for 6 hours ahead (Table 1). For this, neural networks were trained for each pollutant using the datasets from adjacent monitoring stations.

Table 1

Hourly Forecast Accuracy for 6 Hours in Kyiv						
	Forecast for, hours					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Average accuracy, p	0,8384	0,8291	0,7785	0,7492	0,7212	0,7198

The test forecast was conducted based on data from Kyiv over one month, after which the average forecast accuracy for the city was calculated.

Conclusions. An architecture for an intelligent automated system for monitoring and forecasting air pollution in Ukraine has been developed, with a forecasting horizon of up to 6 hours based on open data, achieving the stated objective.

Computational experiments demonstrated that the air pollution forecasting model provides an average accuracy of ($p = 0.72$) over the first 6 hours, surpassing or aligning with the results of existing analogs. The use of an automated information collection system, a proprietary air quality forecasting model, and pollution visualization through mapping services makes the developed solution unique, significantly expanding knowledge in this field.

The system is aimed at protecting public health but also has wide applicability in enterprises, private organizations, and government institutions.

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